

Effect of Human Capital Development on the Performance of Small Scale Enterprises in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

It is globally acknowledged that small-scale businesses (SSEs) play a critical role in promoting innovation, economic growth, employment creation, and social development in both developed and developing nations. SSEs in Nigeria have not contributed as much to the nation's economic development and progress as was anticipated because of a lackluster level of innovation. The performance of SSEs in Ondo State, Nigeria, was therefore investigated in relation to the development of human capital. Out of 2,324 registered SSEs, data from 270 respondents were gathered using a structured questionnaire and a simple random sampling technique. In order to investigate the relationship between the independent variable (human capital development) and the dependent variable (sales growth), the data were analyzed using simple linear regression and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. The results of the study showed that increased sales are positively and significantly impacted by the development of human capital ($\beta = 0.752$, $t = 15.248$, $P < .005$). According to this, sales growth in Ondo State, Nigeria, is strongly predicted by the development of human capital. According to the outcome, the State's sales growth was boosted by 64.7%, in part by human capital development. The study concluded that if sufficient funds are allocated to developing their human capital—particularly through training, seminars, workshops, and the acquisition of academic and professional qualifications—SSEs in Ondo State, Nigeria, can achieve a considerable improvement in both their financial and non-financial performance. Thus, it is therefore recommended that governments, non-governmental organizations, and other interested parties make investments in thorough training and educational initiatives designed to meet the unique requirements of SSEs.

Keywords: *Human capital, HCD, small scale enterprises, medium enterprises.*

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Introduction

Small-scale enterprises (SSEs) play a critical role as development and innovation engines in the changing terrain of modern economies. They are not only important for creating jobs but also for reducing poverty and promoting globally consistent economic growth. The development of human capital is crucial for these businesses because it is the foundation that supports their competitive advantage and operational effectiveness. It is crucial for stakeholders, policymakers, and researchers to comprehend the complex interactions between human capital development and SSE performance since this knowledge can provide valuable insights into boosting productivity, encouraging socioeconomic development, and fostering

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sustainable growth. Frequently acknowledged as the foundation of global economies, SSEs have distinct obstacles and prospects that are greatly impacted by the expertise, proficiencies, and capacities of their workforce. Innovation, productivity, and flexibility within SSEs are mostly fueled by human capital, which is made up of all the individual competences and potentials within a company (Anugwu & Nwosu, 2021).

The development of human capital is essential in this difficult business climate to maintain the highly skilled workforce that will support the shift in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) toward higher value-added activities and increased productivity (Ezeliora, Umeh, & Dilinna, 2020; Ezeliora, Nwakobi, & Aguh, 2017; Ezeliora & Umeh, 2014). The cultivation of a strong entrepreneurial culture and the development of human capital are essential components of human capital development. According to Esparza, Monroy, and Granados (2012), human capital development aids in training that transfers and applies knowledge to fulfill the organization's workforce development goal. This will aid in the survival of these SMEs because training through knowledge transfer and skill development is the linkage between retaining and upgrading human talent with the companies, especially SMEs.

Ezeliora and Umeh (2014) observe that companies are confronting a growing number of obstacles as a result of the dynamic business environment, which forces them to pursue sustainable growth, enhanced performance, competitive advantage, and long-term survival. The rationale is that, in the wake of globalization, businesses now place a greater emphasis on natural resources, including tangible assets like technology, as the primary metric for gauging their strategic advantage (Bakotić, 2016). The most important resources that can be utilized to gauge an organization's competitiveness in the current knowledge-based economy are its intellectual property and human resources (Debrah, Oseghale, and Adams, 2018). Thus, any firm that has strong human resources based on knowledge is typically seen as having an advantage and being able to secure better economic futures (Okoye, 2022; Hadad, 2017).

Statement of the Problem

It is commonly known that small-scale enterprises (SSEs) play a critical role in promoting innovation, economic growth, employment creation, and social development in both developed and developing nations. According to Adeyemo, Gbadeyan, and Brimah (2020), inadequate innovation has prevented SSEs in Nigeria from contributing to the nation's economic growth and development to the extent that was anticipated. The level of innovation in Nigeria is still regarded as poor, despite the appeals for creative activity. The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) reported in 2023 that Nigerian SMEs gave innovation a low priority. Nigeria is not doing nearly as well as it should in promoting innovative practices, as seen by its ranking of 109th out of 132 nations in the World Innovative Index. Though Nigerian small businesses were ranked 11th in Sub-Saharan Africa, this rating highlights a larger problem of insufficient human capital competence and a lack of emphasis on innovation (WIPO, 2023). Notwithstanding a number of government programs and legislative frameworks intended to strengthen SSEs' contributions to the local economy, they continually perform poorly. A gap exists between the intended economic effects of policy and the real ones, as seen by the persisting poverty levels. Investigating the elements preventing SSEs from reaching their full potential is therefore urgently necessary. Accordingly, this study looked at how human capital development influences SSE performance in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of Human Capital Development on the Performance of Small Scale Enterprises in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis of the Study

H₀₁: Human Capital Development has no significant positive effect on the performance of Small Scale Enterprises in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Human Capital

Human capital refers to the knowledge, skills, abilities, and experiences possessed by individuals that contribute to their productive capacity and economic value within a workforce or society. It includes both tangible traits like formal education and training and non-tangible traits like creativity, flexibility, and problem-solving skills. It also refers to procedures involving education, training, and other professional programs meant to raise an employee's knowledge, skills, abilities, values, and societal assets in order to improve their performance and level of satisfaction (Ukenna, Ijeoma, Anionwu, and Olise, 2010). According to Wright, Coff, and Moliterno (2014), human capital is a crucial resource for businesses, particularly when it comes to workers' ongoing development of their knowledge, skills, and talents. It also describes the qualities, aptitudes, and knowledge ingrained in people that support the development of their social, economic, and personal well-being.

According to Subramaniam and Youndt (2005), human capital encompasses all of the knowledge that employees hold, including their unique experiences, values, and know-how. Human capital is the wealth that each employee in the organization possesses and contributes to the business's worth. This component, which includes things like group skills, creative ability, problem-solving capacities, and leadership, is referred to as "human assets" by Subramaniam and Youndt (2005). Human capital is defined as the individual investments people make in their own growth, which positively impact organizational productivity and the country's economic development (Ogunyomi & Bruning, 2015).

Human Capital Development

The process of improving people's skills, knowledge, and talents through education, training, and experience is known as human capital development (HCD). The goal is to increase productivity and potential contributions to social and economic growth by doing this. In order to promote individual development, organizational performance, and general societal advancement, it entails methodical efforts to invest in and nurture human resources (Okoye, 2022). Heathfield (2011) defines HCD as a management strategy that uses training, education, and skill development initiatives to help employees advance both personally and as organizational members and contributors. According to Adeyi, Apansile, Okere, and Okafor (2018), HCD can also be viewed as a good opportunity to train staff members in management so they can coach, mentor, and advise other staff members. Additionally, this HCD method will help workers keep up with organizational growth and changes while allowing employees to carry out their jobs in an effective manner (Iqbal and Ahmad, 2010; Kirkpatrick, 2004). Therefore, when it comes to meeting an organization's current and future task requirements, HCD is regarded as its most important asset.

Unfortunately, due to a historically subpar approach toward training, only a very small number of businesses are able to fully realize the promise of HCD (Alfandi, 2016). Studies reveal that while unemployment rates are rising globally, businesses are finding it difficult to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary to support them in achieving their particular objectives (Alfandi, 2016; Khan & Khan, 2010). The World Economic Forum's (2013) human capital report, which said that "the global economy is entering an era of talent scarcity that, if left unaddressed, will hinder economic growth worldwide," despite severe unemployment in many countries, reinforced this claim. In order to overcome the current economic obstacles and realize the benefits of investing in HCD, it is necessary to strengthen organizational HCD through training, education, and other development activities. These advantages include more output, lower staff turnover, higher efficiency, and eventually fewer supervision requirements.

Small Scale Enterprise

Giving the meaning of SSEs in the context of the study is crucial, especially in light of the claims made by academics that their definition has always been highly contentious and challenging (Eniola 2014). Ekpenyong and Nyong (1992) claim that the subjective assessment used to categorize enterprises as small,

medium, or large is the reason there isn't a widely recognized definition. Furthermore, every nation and its institutions employ different standards based on the goals and policies of organizations, and every nation has a different economy. The definition of SMEs is further complicated by the use of disparate data collection methods and terminologies (Okoye, 2022). However, the definition that is generally accepted and most frequently applied in Nigeria was outlined in the 2015 National Policy on Micro, Small, and Medium-Scale Enterprises (Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN)). The dual criteria of employment and assets (apart from land and buildings) are used in this national policy for classification.

Table 1. Classification of Small and Medium Enterprises

S/N	Size Category	Employment	Assets (Naira, million excluding land and building)
1	Small Enterprises	10 to 49	5 to less than 50
2	Medium Enterprises	50 to 199	50 to less than 500

Source: National Policy on SMEs Report, 2015.

Theoretical Review

Human Capital Theory

According to the theory of human capital, people are valuable resources that boost economic production because of their skills, knowledge, and capacities. The idea, whose roots are in the work of economists like Schultz (1971) and Friedman (1976), highlights the significance of health, education, and training investments in order to increase labor productivity and efficiency. People can become more capable and contribute to growth and higher economic output by developing these human capital traits (Okoye, 2022; Kraiger, McLinden, & Casper, 2004). The development of human capital is clearly a major factor driving corporate performance when SSEs employ the human capital paradigm. Investing in the skills and competencies of their workers can give SSEs, who frequently have fewer resources than larger firms, a major competitive advantage. Improving SSEs' human capital results in better problem-solving, creativity, and adaptability—all of which are critical for meeting the demands of dynamic market conditions. Within this framework, formal education, career training, on-the-job training, and ongoing professional development are some of the techniques that can be included in human capital development within SSEs. SSEs can increase operational effectiveness, encourage innovation, and boost customer satisfaction by developing a workforce that is educated and skilled. Thus, in order to improve the overall performance and competitiveness of SSEs, the theory emphasizes the strategic significance of human capital development, coordinating the personal development of employees with the overarching objectives of the

Empirical Review

Small-scale enterprises (SSEs) are essential to the world's economy because they stimulate employment, innovation, and economic vitality. In an effort to provide knowledge that may guide practice and policy, academics from all around the world have studied how human capital development affects SSE performance in great detail. In order to lay the groundwork for comprehending the impact of human capital development on SSE performance, this study summarizes earlier research, adding to the larger conversation on economic growth and entrepreneurial success.

A study on how human capital development affects small and medium-sized businesses' performance in the South-South Region of Nigeria was carried out by Okoye (2022). Survey research methodology was employed in the study. Based on Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 265 was obtained. The study's population consists of 602 Innoson and 184 Emenite, for a total of 786. Surveys with both closed- and open-ended questions were used by the researcher to get data. Using the t-test statistical tool, the data were evaluated and displayed in frequency, percentage, and mean tables. Organizational success and HCD investment have a strong and favorable association, according to study findings.

Another study on the effects of human capital development on small and medium-sized enterprises in a few chosen organizations in Anambra State, Nigeria, was conducted by Anugwu and Nwosu (2021). In the study, a descriptive survey design was employed. The primary data source for the study was an oral interview conducted with the target staff of Millennium Industries and a structured questionnaire. There are 270 people in the study as a whole. Nonetheless, 259 of the 270 respondents that were employed for the sampling returned their questionnaires fully completed. To test the hypotheses developed for the study, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used, assisted by SPSS software. The study's findings demonstrated how human capital development boosts the performance of businesses in the target area by educating staff to operate SMEs more effectively, increasing SMEs' efficiency, encouraging employee initiative, increasing employees' flexibility, and enhancing employee service delivery.

A study on the effect of human capital on the performance of small and medium-sized businesses in the South West of Nigeria was conducted by Adeyemo, Gbadeyan, and Brimah (2020). The study used a field survey in conjunction with a quantitative research methodology. There were 22,720 small and 570 medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in the research population, all of which focused primarily on the manufacturing and services industries. With the use of stratified selection, 393 operators of SMEs were chosen as the sample. A structured questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale was used to get information from the respondents. The data were analyzed using both inferential and descriptive statistical approaches. Linear regression analysis was utilized to assess the study's hypothesis. The results of this study demonstrated that human capital significantly and favorably affects the performance of SMEs. Thus, this study proposed that in order for SMEs to operate at their best, they should focus on hiring highly qualified, imaginative, intelligent, and driven employees.

Okafor, Ofobruku, Obi-Anike and Agbaeze (2019) conducted research to find out how staff performance in a Nigerian public hospital was impacted by human capital development. Despite government efforts to build human resources, employee performance issues in Nigerian public hospitals continue to exist. Using the statistics produced from the model developed for the three hypotheses, the data gathered from the survey questionnaire were examined and tested. The statistical method of linear regression was used to examine the gathered data. The findings showed that hospitals in Nigeria can maximize staff performance by implementing human capital development initiatives. The study discovered, in particular, that the weak employee performance in Nigerian hospitals was caused by a lack of a clear human resource development strategy targeted at bridging recognized skills, knowledge, and attitude gaps.

In Lagos State, Nigeria, Dawodu, Akintunde, and Olulana (2018) studied organizational performance and human capital development in the food, beverage, and tobacco industries. Given its paramount relevance in any productive organization, the function of human capital in converting raw materials into final goods and services cannot be overstated. The entire set of 276 returned questionnaire copies was utilized for data analysis. The research questionnaire was distributed using a stratified random sampling technique based on the job categorization of the respondents in each of the seven organizations. The study tested the research hypothesis using the Pearson coefficient of correlation. The coefficient of correlation showed that organizational performance and human capital development are significantly correlated.

Methodology

A survey design was used in the investigation. Ondo State served as the study area. This location was chosen for convenience and purpose. Out of the two thousand, three hundred and twenty-four (2,324) SSE owners registered with the Ondo State Ministry of Commerce and Industry (NBS-SMEDAN, 2017), a total of two hundred and eighty-four (284) were chosen using a formula proposed by Krejcie and Morgan (2002) through multistage sampling procedures that included stratified, purposive sampling, and simple random sampling techniques. Three local governments from each of the state's three senatorial districts made up the nine (09) local government areas that made up the sample.

Nine local governments—Akure South, Akure North, Ondo West, Owo, Akoko North-East, Ose, Odigbo, Ilaje, and Okitipupa—were chosen for this study. Primary data were gathered from the respondents using a structured questionnaire. Respondents were given 284 questionnaire copies; of those, 273 were retrieved, or 96.1% of the total collected. Out of the 273 copies that were returned, three were incompletely filled and hence not included in the analysis. This meant that a total of 270 replies were available for analysis. Each component of the questionnaire consisted of seven items, and the responses were scored using a Likert-scale format, with responses ranging from 1–5 (1 being strongly disagree and 5 being strongly agree). A group of specialists was asked to validate the instrument employed in this investigation. The test-retest procedure, which entails administering the same instrument twice to fifteen (15) SSE owners from each of the chosen local government areas but outside the sample area during a two-week interval, was also used to test the instrument's reliability. Remarks from the pilot test-retest were also taken into account. In order to assess the reliability and soundness of the HCD and SSE performance, the study reported Cronbach reliability alphas of .74 and .71, respectively, which met the study's acceptance criteria. The data were analyzed using simple linear regression analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

Results and Discussion

Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

The descriptive analysis of the respondents' profiles revealed that 33.2% of them were women and 66.8% of them were men. The results therefore made it evident that more men than women replied. This implies that a greater number of men were pursuing economic endeavors. This distribution could be explained by the fact that most third-world countries have a cultural bias for male involvement in economic activities over female engagement. According to the results, 20.0 percent of respondents were between the ages of 36 and 45, and 3.8 percent were between the ages of 46 and 55. Additionally, 40.0 percent and 36.2 percent of the respondents were between the ages of 18 and 25, or 26 and 35, respectively. This implies that most small business owners are still very young, active, and full of life. It also suggests that they have the potential to continue contributing significantly to the Ondo State subsector's economic growth.

The marital status of the respondents was as follows: 4.9% were single, 11.0% were divorced, 14.5% were separated, and 69.6% were married. The research indicates that more responsible men and women engage in small-scale business operations because the majority of respondents were married. The following details about the respondents' educational backgrounds were once again made public: A first degree, an HND, or an equivalent was held by 45.3% of the population, a primary school leaving certificate or SSCE or equivalent by 3.7%, a master's degree or other higher degree by none, and teachers grade II, ND, NCE, or equivalent by 51.0%. The majority of Oyo State respondents, according to the findings, possessed at least a teacher's grade II, ND, NCE, or an equivalent. This implies that the majority of Ondo State's small business owners had a good education.

When comparing the years of experience of the respondents to the selected small business owners, it was discovered that 60.7 percent of them had been in their small businesses for between five and ten years, 39.3% had founded their companies between eleven and sixteen years earlier, and none had been in them for fewer than five years. According to the study's results, most participants had been running their small businesses for five to ten years. This implies that the participants had acquired a reasonable degree of business acumen over a considerable duration, which considerably aided the investigator in obtaining reliable data for the investigation.

H₀₁: Human capital development has no significant effect on the performance of small scale enterprises in Ondo State

Table 1. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.821 ^a	.674	.614	7.197

Note: a. Predictor: (Constant), Human capital development

Table 2a presents the model summary of the regression analysis examining the relationship between SSE performance and human capital development, with an R value of .821. This implies a close connection between the performance of SSEs in the research region and the development of human capital. At a significance level of 5%, the degree of the correlation is likewise statistically significant. The SSE performance in the selected SSEs in the study area is over 67% explained by human capital development, as indicated by the R square value of .674. Other factors that are not included in this model but are represented in the stochastic error term account for the remaining 33% of the variability.

Table 2. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1676.821	1	1676.821	4.196	.000 ^b
	Residual	1160.242	282	65.518		
	Total	2837.063	283			

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Sales Growth; b. Predictors: (Constant), Human capital development

Table 2b indicates that the model's overall significance is F (1, 283), 4.196, P-value, or sig value 0.05 (Sig 0.000). It is evident that there is substantial evidence against the null hypothesis because there is a better than 5% chance that it will be rejected. In terms of the goodness of fit (4.196), the result of $F_{tab}(1, 283) > F_{cal}$ indicates the substantial statistical significance of the entire regression model.

Table 3. Simple Regression Analysis Showing the Effect of Human Capital Development on the Performance of SSEs in Ondo State, Nigeria

Model		Unstandardised Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	46.283	1.642		15.248	.000
	Human capital development	1.341	.137	.752	12.171	.000

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Sales Growth

The growth of SSEs in Ondo State, Nigeria, is significantly positively impacted by the development of human capital ($\beta = 0.752$, $t = 15.248$, $P < .001$), according to Table 2c. This suggests that when human capital is developed through entrepreneurial activities, the study area's economic performance improves in terms of, among other things, increased sales, the creation of jobs, per capita income, and the decrease of poverty. Additionally, Table 1a shows that an increase in SSE owners' entrepreneurial competencies contributed 67.4% (with an R^2 of 0.674 and a $F = 4.196$) to the sales growth of SSEs in the State. The remaining 32.6% of the sales growth may have resulted from unrelated variables that this study did not capture. The results of this study are consistent with those of Okoye (2022), Anugwu and Nwosu (2021), and Adeyemo et al. (2020), which showed that human capital development contributes to the improvement of the performance of businesses in the studied area by training employees for higher performance of SMEs, increasing SMEs' efficiency, influencing employees' proactivity, increasing employees' flexibility, and enhancing employees' service delivery.

Conclusion

The performance of SSEs in Ondo State, Nigeria, was studied in relation to the development of human capital. Evidence of the connection between HCD investment and SSE performance was provided by the study. The study's significance lies in its focus on the necessity for SSEs to provide their owners and staff with ongoing training so they may guarantee that they have the information, abilities, and skills needed to provide high-quality goods and services that will enhance their organizational performance. The study concludes, based on the aforementioned data, that SSEs in Ondo State, Nigeria, can achieve a noteworthy improvement in their non-financial and financial performance provided sufficient resources are allocated to the development of their human capital, particularly through academic and professional credential acquisition, training, seminars, and workshops.

Recommendations

The study found that small-scale enterprises (SSEs) in Ondo State, Nigeria, perform far better when human capital development is prioritized. As a result, it was advised that players in the public and private sectors make investments in thorough training and educational initiatives designed to meet the unique requirements of SSEs. In order to strengthen management and technical competencies, this should involve skill development workshops, vocational training, and ongoing professional education. To further establish a supportive atmosphere for these businesses, laws that ease access to data, technology, and capital should be reinforced. Prioritizing the development of human capital will boost innovation and productivity while ensuring the competitiveness and sustainable expansion of SSEs in the area.

References

- Adeyemo, S. A., Gbadeyan, R. A. & Brimah, A. N. (2020). Impact of human capital on the performance of small and medium enterprises in South West, Nigeria. *The International Journal Of Business & Management*, 8(3), 208-215. <http://dx.doi.org/10.24940/theijbm/2020/v8/i3/BM2003-063>
- Adeyi, A.O., Apansile, E.K., Okere, W. & Okafor, L.I. (2018). Training and development and organisational performance: standpoint from private tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics, Management and Trade*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.9734/JEMT%2F2018%2F44895>
- Alfandi, A. M. (2016). Training impact on the performance of employees: A case of Jordanian travel and tourism institutions. *International Business Management*, 10(4), 377–384. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3923/ibm.2016.377.384>
- Anugwu, C. C. & Nwosu, K. C. (2021). Impact of human capital development on small and medium scale enterprise in some selected firms in Anambra State. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 21(18), 57-64. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2021/v21i1830499>
- Bakotić, D. (2016). Relationship between job satisfaction and organizational performance. *Economic Research-Ekonomska istraživanja*, 29(1), 118–130. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2016.1163946>
- Dawodu, A. A. Akintunde, O. A. & Olulana, B. S. (2018). Human Capital Development and Organizational Performance in the Food, Beverage and Tobacco Industry in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Studies*, 18(2), 27-35.
- Debrah, Y.A., Oseghale, R.O. & Adams, K. (2018). Human capital, innovation and international competitiveness in Sub-Saharan Africa', in Adeleye, I. and Esposito, M. (eds). *Africa's Competitiveness in the Global Economy*. Palgrave Macmillan 219–248.
- Ekpenyong, D.B. & Nyong, M.O. (1992). *Small and medium enterprises in Nigeria: Their characteristics, problems and sources of fund*. African Economic Research Consortium, Nairobi.

- Eniola, A.A. (2014). The role of SME firm performance in Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (OMAN Chapter)*, 3(12), 33. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0016552>
- Ezeliora, C. D., Umeh, M. N. & Dilinna, A. M. (2020). Investigation and optimization of production variables: A case of plastic manufacturing industry. *Journal of Engineering Research and Reports*, 15(1),1-16. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jerr/2020/v15i117134>
- Ezeliora, C. D., Nwakobi, J. O. & Aguh, S. P. (2017). Appraisal of optimal production quantity in small and medium scale industry. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Technology (IJAERT)*, 5(1).
- Ezeliora, C. D., Umeh, M. N., Mbeledogou, N. N. & Ezeokonkwo, J. U. (2014). Improving the productivity of small and medium scale industries using linear programming model. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 5(1), 2009-2025.
- Esparza, P., Monroy, N. & Granados, F. (2012). Managerial effectiveness in small enterprises: Implications for HRD. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 23(1), 25-35. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090599910253519>
- Friedman, M. (1968). *The role of monetary policy*. Essential readings in economics, 215–231.
- Hadad, S. (2017). Knowledge economy: Characteristics and dimensions. *Management Dynamics in the Knowledge Economy*, 5(2), 203–225. <http://dx.doi.org/10.25019/MDKE/5.2.03>
- Heathfield, S.M. (2011). What People Want From Work: Motivation - Motivation Is Different For Each of Your Employees.
- Iqbal, M.J. & Ahmad, M. (2010). Enhancing quality of education through e-learning: the case study of Allama Iqbal Open University. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 11(1), 84–97.
- Khan, H.U.Z. & Khan, R. (2010). Human capital disclosure practices of top Bangladeshi companies. *Journal of Human Resource Costing & Accounting*, 14(4), 329–349. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14013381011105984>
- Kirkpatrick, D. L. (2004). *Evaluating Training Programs: The Four Levels*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Kraiger, K., McLinden, D. & Casper, W.J. (2004). Collaborative planning for training impact. *Human Resource Management*, 43(4), 337-351. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/hrm.20028>
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (2002). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(1), 607-610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447003000308>
- National MSMEs Survey (2015). Draft National Policy on micro, small and medium enterprises in Nigeria, Federal Republic of Nigeria.
- NBS-SMEDAN (2017). National Survey of Micro Small & Medium Enterprises (MSMEs).
- Ogunyomi, P. & Bruning, N. S. (2015). Human resource management and organizational performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 5(7), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2015.1033640>
- Okafor, C. N. Ofobruku, S. A., Obi-Anike, H. O. & Agbaeze, E. K. (2019). An investigation of the effect of human capital development on employees' performance in Nigeria Public Hospitals: A Study of the Federal Medical Hospital Keffi. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 2(3), 234-246.
- Okoye, E. O. (2022). Effect of Human Capital Development on the Performance of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises in the South-South Region of Nigeria. *Contemporary Journal of Management*, 4(5), 48-61. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7149939>
- Schultz, T.W. (1961). Investment in Human Capital. *American Economic Review*, 51, 1-17.

Subramaniam, M. & Youndt, M. A. (2005). The Influence of intellectual capital on the types of innovation capabilities. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48(3), 450-463. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2005.17407911>

Ukenna, S., Ijeoma, N., Anionwu, C. and Olise, M.C. (2010). Effect of investment in human capital development on organisational performance: Empirical examination of the perception of small business owners in Nigeria. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 26, 93–107.

World Economic Forum. (2013). The Human Capital Report 2013. Retrieved from <http://reports.weforum.org/humancapital-index-2013/>

World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) (2023). *Global Innovation Index 2023: Innovation in the face of uncertainty*. Geneva: WIPO. <https://doi.org/10.34667/tind.48220>

Wright, P. M., Coff, R. & Moliterno, T. P. (2014). Strategic human capital: Crossing the great divide. *Journal of Management*, 40, 353-370. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206313518437>